

Reliability Study of Au-In Transient Liquid Phase Bonding for SiC Power Semiconductor Packaging

Brian Grummel^{1,2}, Habib A. Mustain^{1,3}, Z. John Shen¹, and Allen R. Hefner²

¹Dept. of Electrical Engineering and
Computer Science
University of Central Florida
Orlando, FL USA,
bgrummel@mail.ucf.edu

²Semiconductor Electronics Division
Physical Measurement Laboratory
National Institute of Standards and
Technology
Gaithersburg, MD USA

³Cree, Inc.
Durham, NC USA
(Current Affiliation)

Abstract—Transient liquid phase (TLP) bonding is a promising advanced die-attach technique for wide-bandgap power semiconductor and high-temperature packaging. TLP bonding advances modern soldering techniques by raising the melting point to over 500 °C without detrimental high-lead materials. The bond also has greater reliability and rigidity due in part to a bonding temperature of 200 °C that drastically lowers the peak bond stresses. Furthermore, the thermal conductivity is fractionally increased 67 % while the bond thickness is substantially reduced, lowering the thermal resistance by an order of magnitude or more. It is observed that Au-In TLP bonds exude excellent electrical reliability against thermal cycling degradation if designed properly as experimentally confirmed in this work.

I. INTRODUCTION

As SiC and other wide bandgap power semiconductor devices gain increasing acceptance in the marketplace, it becomes increasingly important to develop high temperature packaging technologies that allow for higher operating temperatures for applications in extreme environments and to reduce the size, weight, cost, and complexity of thermal management systems. Traditional lead-based die-attach solders have a melting temperature below 200°C and are incapable of supporting the high-temperature operation of SiC MOSFETs that have been demonstrated to operate up to 500 °C for an extended period [1].

An ideal wide-bandgap die-attach material system needs to have a high melting temperature, high thermal conductivity, low mechanical stress, and high tensile and yield strength [2]. Transient liquid phase (TLP) bonding is a novel die-attach method for power devices capable of providing these qualities. Several papers, primarily on proof-of-concept studies, have looked into the TLP bonding technique, but have not investigated its electrical reliability or attempted to characterize multiple bond structures [3]. This work expands the prior work in the field of TLP bonding. It is intended to characterize multiple TLP bond compositions and to investigate bond reliability over temperature cycling conditions by monitoring changes in thin film resistivity and surface morphology of specially fabricated test structures. The

influence of indium composition on reliability in the gold-indium (Au-In) TLP bond with thermal cycling is also studied.

II. TRANSIENT LIQUID PHASE BONDING

A TLP bond is composed primarily of two materials, a base layer which has a high melting point and an interlayer which has a much lower melting point and a high diffusion rate into the base layer. To utilize TLP bonding as a die-attach method, the base material is typically deposited on a substrate or a semiconductor die while the interlayer is deposited on the adjoining piece. The two are then put in contact with applied pressure at a temperature above the interlayer melting point causing it to quickly melt and diffuse into the base layer. The bond becomes stable by being held at the melting temperature until the interlayer is completely consumed into the base; this is known as isothermal solidification [4]. An example of our TLP bonding experiment is shown in Fig. 1 where a SiC Schottky rectifier die is TLP bonded to a silicon nitride DBC substrate. Fig. 2 shows the I-V characteristics of the packaged SiC rectifier.

The advantage of this technique is that the resulting compound of the base and interlayer materials become one solid TLP bond with a melting temperature significantly higher than that of the original interlayer material but is joined at a much lower temperature. This reduces the total mechanical stress applied to the die-attach and device throughout its operation over a wide temperature range and increases reliability, one of the greatest concerns for die-attach techniques. This is a large improvement over alternative high-temperature brazes.

III. EXPERIMENT

While the complete SiC device package shown in Fig. 1 represents the final solution, it is difficult to observe the variations in thin film electrical properties and surface morphology in the TLP bonds over thermal cycling with these structures. To this end, we have designed and fabricated several special TLP bond test structures with all TLP and barrier metal layers sequentially deposited on a glass substrate as opposed to forming an actual bond of a substrate on a

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Figure 1. Figure 2. SiC Schottky rectifier TLP bonded to a silicon nitride DBC substrate with copper metallization.

Figure 2. I-V characteristics of a SiC Schottky rectifier TLP bonded on a silicon nitride DBC substrate.

semiconductor die. Glass is chosen as our substrate due to its electrical insulation along with its coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) comparable to that of SiC and silicon nitride. While this test structure is not a true representation of the real TLP device package shown in Fig. 1, it does offer an opportunity to measure the thin film resistivity of the Au-In bond and its variation over temperature cycling as well as observe any changes in surface morphology. The material stack is shown in Fig. 3.

A base layer of gold with a melting point of 1064 °C along with an indium interlayer with a melting point of 156 °C is used as this has been shown to be a workable material pair for TLP bonding [5-7].

As an extension over the prior TLP work, we investigated

Figure 3. Material stack of TLP samples emulating actual TLP bonds. Au and In thicknesses vary by sample to create different material ratios seen in Table 1.

TABLE I. TLP SAMPLE PARAMETERS

Sample	t_{In} (μm)	t_{Au} (μm)	Indium Mass Fraction, w_B	Indium Mole Fraction, χ_B
A	1.261	1.0	0.323	0.45
B	3.087	1.0	0.538	0.67
C	3.087	0.223	0.84	0.90

three different Au-In TLP bonds with three different mole fractions of In. Bond TLP-A has a relatively high concentration of Au in the bond with an In mole fraction of 0.45 while bond TLP-B is proportioned to form AuIn_2 compound throughout the bond as opposed to forming multiple Au-In material phases, this occurs at an In mole fraction of 0.67. TLP-C has the highest In composition with an In mole fraction of 0.90. In this particular sample, there may be pure In remaining after reacting with the available Au to form Au-In compounds, possibly causing instability in the final bond. The three samples are summarized in Table 1 and identified on the Au-In phase diagram in Fig. 4 [8].

Each of the three Au-In TLP bonds are sandwiched within a stack of barrier layers of tungsten for adhesion, titanium as the primary diffusion barrier, and platinum to prevent undesirable Au-Ti intermetallics [9], [10]. All barrier layers are added to both the glass substrates along with the exposed face of the TLP bond to completely emulate the entire material stack that is present when utilizing TLP as a bond, as in Fig. 1.

All samples are fabricated by first electron beam evaporating 47 nm of W followed by 150 nm of Ti and then 30 nm of Pt. The TLP-A samples are then deposited with 1.261 μm In while the B and C substrates receive 3.087 μm of In. All samples are then e-beam evaporated with 50 nm of Au as a temporary oxidation barrier before transferring the samples out of the e-beam system and immediately into a sputtering system. TLP-A and B substrates are then sputtered

Figure 4. Binary phase diagram of the Au-In system with three test sample concentrations denoted at mole fractions of indium 0.45, 0.67, and 0.90 within samples TLP-A, B, and C, respectively.

Figure 5. Logarithmic graph of resistivity measurements of samples TLP-A, B, and C versus thermal cycling degradation showing excellent reliability in higher Au concentration samples A and B while the sample, C, containing high In exuded poor reliability with increasing resistivity. Standard deviation error graphed with $n = 20$.

with 777 nm of Au before the C samples are placed into the chamber. All samples are then completed by sputtering an additional 173 nm of Au followed by the stack of barrier layers again but in reverse order of 30 nm of Pt, 150 nm of Ti, then 47 nm of W to complete the test structure. Though Au is deposited in two or three depositions, the total Au thickness is calculated to create the desired In mole fraction in each of the samples. The slides are then loaded into a 200 °C oven and immediately purged with nitrogen and then vacuum pumped to 1.44 kPa for 15 min. They are then removed and allowed to cool in air to complete the TLP samples.

To characterize the electrical reliability of the TLP bonds, the samples are temperature cycled in air to simulate the operating conditions that power electronics experience from self-heating, extreme-temperature environments, or both. The thermal cycles ramp between 25 °C and 200 °C at a rate of 20 °C/min with a dwell at 25 °C and 200 °C for 5 min each for a total cycle of approximately 30 min.

IV. RESULTS

A. Resistivity

Each sample is tested for its thin film resistivity before and after thermal cycling and is shown in Fig. 5. All resistivity measurements are taken using a four point probe with probe currents of both 10.0 mA and 9.0 mA measured at five specified locations uniformly distributed over the sample surface during each characterization. The measurements are then averaged to create a mean resistivity value. Initially, the high Au concentration sample, TLP-A, has a resistivity of $\rho_A = 38.9 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$ while the samples TLP-B and TLP-C hold lower resistivity values of $\rho_B = 14.067 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$ and $\rho_C = 14.356 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$.

After 100 thermal cycles, there is no observation of change in resistivity in samples TLP-A and TLP-B with higher Au concentrations, while TLP-C with the highest In concentration shows a large increase in resistivity indicating degradation of this Au-In TPL bond. After only 200 thermal cycles, the resistivity of TLP-C has fractionally increased 78 % to $\rho_C = 25.66 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$ and by 83.23 % after 800 cycles to $\rho_C = 26.3 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$. The large resistivity increase is

partially due to in-homogeneity of resistivity over the surface of the sample with some areas rising greatly while others remain lower at $\rho \approx 20 \mu\Omega \cdot cm$. This non-uniformity is the primary cause for the increased standard deviation seen in the graph as well. Over the same period of 800 cycles, TLP-A has fractionally risen only 2.43 % and TLP-B just 1.38 % indicating little change within the TLP bond.

There is also a highly visible change in the color of the TLP-C surface in response to the thermal cycling which, as seen in Fig. 6, has gone from the original brown color created primarily by the exterior W layer to a gray color indicative of In presence. The color of the TLP-A and TLP-B samples remain brown and only slightly increase in darkness with thermal cycling, with TLP-B again showing the most reliable results of little color change.

B. Surface Microscopy and Diffusion

SEM inspection of the samples reveals no morphological changes in the fine structure surface of the samples as a result of thermal cycling on all three samples, thus appearing identical to their un-degraded counterparts, as seen in Fig. 7. This is an indicator of isothermal solidification during the sample preparation as this unchanged morphology would

Figure 6. Surface color change of TLP samples due to thermal cycling. Original sample surface color displayed above surface color after 400 thermal cycles on samples TLP-A, B, and C.

Figure 7. SEM microscopy of surface morphologies of degraded samples at 25 000 X magnification. Appearance of these samples is identical to the original morphologies prior to thermal cycling (*not pictured*).

likely not occur if a layer of pure In were in existence within the bond and was melting with each thermal cycle. It therefore is also an indicator of adverse In diffusion out of the TLP bond in sample TLP-C.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy of the samples confirms this hypothesis and reveals diffusion within the bonds which also explains the change in resistivities. The TLP-A and B samples, exhibiting little resistivity variation, show only a small increase in the In concentration near the surface which is expected with continued homogenization of the TLP bond during cycling. The In concentration near the TLP-C surface has increased more significantly and has affected the TLP barrier layers due to indium's high

diffusivity showing high volatility in the sample and the cause of the increase in measured resistivity.

V. CONCLUSION

It has been demonstrated that TLP bonding is a viable method for high-temperature die-attach for SiC and other wide-bandgap power semiconductors in terms of its electrical reliability. Samples TLP-A and B, with optimum Au-In compositions, have shown a negligible rise in resistivity in response to thermal cycling while also maintaining a stable surface morphology and predictable diffusion. Alternatively, sample TLP-C contains an In concentration exceeding what is necessary for proper Au-In bonding and has demonstrated poor thermal cycle reliability. For this reason, Au-In TLP bonds below an In mole fraction of 0.67 remain a very promising die-attach method for SiC devices. It is worthwhile to continue electrical reliability testing of the TLP bonds that have shown promising results in this work while also expanding to perform a robust mechanical reliability investigation utilizing SiC devices and silicon nitride substrates as well.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thankfully note that research performed in part at the NIST Center for Nanoscale Science and Technology.

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